

Lizards and Lies

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Introduction

Lizards and Lies is a two-versus-two board game that models how problematic information (Jack, 2017) moves through social media. Initially designed as a research project trying to simulate the flow of information online, the game has since been adapted for late high school and university classrooms. At its core, Lizards and Lies shows the push-and-pull of false or misleading content online. Themed around conspiracy theories, the game has players take on the role of a malign actor spreading false ideas or those trying to manage the fallacy. By having players work in teams against one another, they explore the challenges and strengths of actors, including: Digital Literacy Educators, platform moderators, conspiracy theorists, and online trolls. Through gameplay and a facilitated debrief, Lizards and Lies demonstrates how information systems are interconnected and the core challenges of managing the large volume of false content being created and consumed. It was initially designed in 2021 by a PhD candidate at Concordia University (Scott DeJong – also author of this write-up) as part of a class on wargaming, before becoming a more robust educational version with the support of Dr. Fenwick McKelvey and their research project exploring online recommendation systems in 2022.

Facts

Release date:	January 2023
Developer:	Scott DeJong, TheGameCrafter (Manufacturer)
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–4
Format:	Synchronous Board Game
Time frame:	1.5 to 2.5 hours
Languages:	English, French, Lithuanian
Environment:	Tables and Chairs. Small Groups
Material:	Board game components; facilitation guide available for download.
Price:	94.99\$ or Free to Print and Play

Resonance & Criticism

Upon its initial release, the game received widespread media attention, with coverage in news and magazine stories that helped boost its visibility beyond its origins in Montreal. Throughout 2022 and 2023, the game was brought to various institutions to spark discussion about the state of disinformation. The designers worked with military groups in Canada, embassies, and professors to develop versions of the game tailored to their contexts and needs. Feedback was gathered at all of these events, and the game was slightly adjusted to address these needs until the project's completion in 2023. At that point, the game was made publicly available on a website for download (lizardsandlies.ca) and purchasable copies through self-publisher The Game Crafter. Additionally, a how-to-play video was recorded and published to help individuals access and play the game. This is also accompanied by a facilitation guide available with the game materials.

At this time, there is no empirical evidence or studies on the efficacy of the game, though its design process of integrating theory has been written and published (DeJong & Souza, 2022).

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Example gameplay setup from *Lizards and Lies*, illustrating the board, player roles, and the circulation of problematic information within the game system (Scott DeJong, *TheGameCrafter*). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Grounded in a story about an ongoing election and the impact of conspiracy theories, players focus on spreading or stopping the spread of messages on social media (see Figure 1). In a two-team alternating-turns game, each player's role gives them particular strengths and weaknesses that reflect the push and pull of content on social media, as researchers have discussed (Han, 2017). Conspiracy theorists build communities to make content go viral, working alongside their allies, the trolls, who target specific groups to generate engagement. However, they follow a predictable playbook, and their content becomes repetitive, making them easier to stop if they do not receive enough visibility. Alternatively, platform moderators try to manage content within communities; however, they can get overwhelmed by the volume of false narratives and need to triage their efforts to focus on the communities most vulnerable. Their ally, Digital Literacy Educators, relies on teaching users to fact-check, but this is a slow, unreliable process that can make it hard to stop content from gaining traction. Each action players take reflects the game's objectives and theories, and facilitation during and after play is meant to help players understand the learning goals.

By playing their own character, players get a glimpse of the challenges and strengths of various actors involved in the proliferation of information online. They are rewarded each round for how successfully they achieved their goals, and the team dynamics are meant to promote social interaction between players. The game's design builds on research on information flows, which explored various analogies for disinformation, such as war and virality, before developing a model of digital ecosystems (DeJong & Souza, 2022). This was coupled with emerging literature on inoculation theory, which suggests that showing how these systems work makes individuals less vulnerable to their effects (Grace & Liang, 2023). The game used the tension of teams battling to prompt players to reflect on malign actors and those trying to deal with false information.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Lizards and Lies has two central objectives. First, it wants players to understand the push and pull of false information movements. Second, it wants to model digital systems to have players learn about the strengths and weaknesses of various actors in the online ecosystem. The former is achieved through reflection on each round of gameplay, and the latter through individual play. As players alternate turns, they will watch as malign actors fill the board with false information, while moderators and educators attempt to remove the content. As content is added and removed, the mechanics allow some false ideas to linger each round, growing larger the next turn, reflecting what Byun Hal Chun (2017) refers to as the bubbling up and swarm of information.

For the second objective, individual mechanics from player cards and boards help them reflect these roles. For example, trolls follow a playbook to manipulate communities, conspiracy theorists always add content where their supporters are, and platform moderators have to manage the flagging and removal of content. This can make the game confusing for less

experienced players and requires a facilitator who is knowledgeable about the game and its material. While the research team has run the game with groups up to 100, they needed some minor facilitation support, which generally translates to one facilitator for every three to four games (12-16 people). In some scenarios, we have players work in pairs, expanding the 4-player variant to 8 players to help give the students and teachers more space for conversation and reflection.

To support student learning, *Lizards and Lies* offers a facilitation guide to potential users and employs an in-between-round narrative to ground the mechanics in the learning goals. As a simulation-style game, the narrative is meant to translate the micro-interactions among players, their cards, and the board into real-world impacts.

Effectiveness

Unfortunately, this game was not evaluated for its learning efficacy in the classroom context. Instead, research focused on the game's design and model (DeJong & Souza, 2022). Reflecting on the simulation and its design, the team examined how the various analogies used to discuss disinformation and its spread struggled to fully encapsulate the issue. Narratives of a disinformation war or virus perpetuate a binary of good actor versus bad actor and a single solution (i.e., vaccine), yet, through design-as-research, the project examined how ecological models of media better reflect the challenges that social media brings to disinformation. The evidence for this was in how the game design and flow developed alongside each analogy. An ecological model provided greater agency for players in the game while also better reflecting the push-and-pull that was core to its design (DeJong & Souza, 2022).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

In its design, the team sought to avoid ongoing political conspiracies or real-world tensions and instead defaulted to playful narratives such as lizard people or aliens. Unfortunately it was only recognized at a later stage of the design process that the origins of the lizard-people conspiracy theory are rooted in anti-Semitic narratives. The game does not seek to perpetuate these associations and addresses this issue explicitly in the facilitation guide. Nevertheless, it acknowledges that, in some contexts, alternative narrative framings would have been more appropriate. Additionally, the game presents the theory in a satirical light, framing it as a conspiracy theory and using play mechanics and flavor text on cards to foster a critical perspective on conspiracy theories and build resilience against misinformation surrounding them. The theory is presented alongside a guided learning process to not only have students become critical of such problematic claims, but also use it as a larger example for class discussion.

However, given that the game's larger goal is based on false information and that such work typically perpetuates harmful narratives, there is space for facilitators to engage players in a meaningful discussion about how seemingly humorous conspiracies have roots in hate. The

game encourages a broader conversation about the theories within it and how they perpetuate false and misleading perspectives among the public in ways that are normalized. Teachers running the game should be aware of this potential conversation when introducing it into their practice.

The game does present several challenges. It is complex, lengthy, and expensive, creating challenges in its distribution and use. While it has been played with 10-year-olds, the level of gameplay and knowledge required make it generally suited for an older audience. Furthermore, given the game's length, it can be challenging to run in a single high school class, making it most suitable for university-level courses. However, the game's topic and intricacy also make it interesting for other groups, highlighting the variety of interests in media literacy tools across industries.

Reviewer(s): Kevin Rebecchi, Elizabeth Peacock

Sources

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